

Expanding ASIA to GAVIDOTTIR : GAMut of Vaccine Induced Damage emphasizing Off Target Immune Responses

Vinu Arumugham
Oct 2019
vinucubeacc@gmail.com

Introduction

Shoenfeld et al. introduced ASIA (Autoimmune/Autoinflammatory Syndrome Induced by Adjuvants) (1). Today many vaccines are subunit vaccines that are weakly immunogenic. Numerous vaccines therefore contain adjuvants which enhance the immune response to enable the vaccine to work (2). Manufacturing vaccines involves the use of growth media for viruses and bacteria which are plant and animal derived (3,4). There are also excipients used in the vaccines that are also derived from plants or animals. Further, recombinant vaccines can use genetically engineered organisms such as yeast and E. coli. Such vaccines contain yeast and E. coli proteins.

World Health Organization (WHO) clean room standards allow thousands of fine dust particles per cubic meter. So vaccine manufacturing facilities compliant with WHO standards will still result in aeroallergen contamination of vaccines. Further many vaccines are offered in multi-dose vials or require reconstitution at the end user site, which results in further aeroallergen contamination (5). Therefore vaccines contain food proteins, aeroallergens, plant/animal/fungal proteins and non-target bacterial/viral proteins. As a result they generate numerous off-target immune responses targeting all these antigens. Such responses cause numerous diseases including food allergies, asthma, autism and autoimmune disorders.

Discussion

ASIA covers autoimmune diseases induced by adjuvanted vaccines. ASIA covers disorders related to immune responses that target self antigens, induced by adjuvanted vaccines. However, we have autoimmune disorders caused by non-adjuvanted vaccines. Non-adjuvanted influenza vaccines induce diseases such as Guillain-Barre Syndrome (GBS) and Myasthenia Gravis (6). We have food protein containing vaccines that induce immune response directed against food proteins which result in diseases such as life-threatening food allergies (7–10), autism (10–12), eosinophilic esophagitis (10,13), etc.. We have seasonal/perennial allergies, asthma and gastroesophageal diseases that are due to immune responses targeting aeroallergen which can be induced either by adjuvanted or non-adjuvanted vaccines (5,10). We have immune response targeted against commensal organisms such as yeast or E. coli that result in disorders such as dysbiosis, atopic dermatitis etc (10,14,15).

GAVIDOTTIR (GAMut of Vaccine Induced Damage emphasizing Off Target Immune Responses) is introduced as a “catch-all” class to cover all diseases caused by such undesirable vaccine induced responses including autoimmune diseases covered by ASIA. GAVIDOTTIR also includes diseases such as type 1 diabetes (10,16–18), neuromyelitis spectrum disorders (NMOSD) (19), rheumatoid arthritis (14,20), celiac disease (21), cardiovascular diseases (10), obesity (10), type 2 diabetes (10) etc. Since off-target immune responses can target any part of the body, diseases classified as GAVIDOTTIR will continue to be discovered.

Vaccines also induce numerous diseases by mechanisms other than off-target immune responses. GAVIDOTTIR covers such damage as well. Below are some examples of such damage.

Multiple sclerosis

Multiple sclerosis is induced by subclinical *B. pertussis* colonization (22). Subclinical colonization occurs due to the failure of the pertussis vaccine to produce mucosal immunity.

Glioma

Natural varicella infection protects against glioma (23). Varicella vaccination can therefore increase glioma incidence.

Shingles

Varicella infection among children protect adults from shingles (24). Varicella vaccination increases shingles prevalence.

Measles

Subcutaneous injection of live virus vaccines introduce live virus on to damaged nerves. This results in encephalitis. Encephalitis is therefore a known MMR vaccine injury listed in the vaccine injury table of the Vaccine Injury Compensation Program (25). Injections/vaccines during persistent measles infection can also result in nervous system access for the viruses thus resulting in encephalitis or Subacute sclerosing panencephalitis (SSPE).

Vaccines cause loss of protection in infants due to poor vaccine induced immunity in the mother. Waning short term vaccine induced immunity exposes adults to risk of measles related complications.

Polio and Acute Flaccid Myelitis

Natural polio is a harmless disease. Any injection when the polio virus is circulating provides the virus with access to nerves which results in crippling disease and complications. Same may apply to acute flaccid myelitis (26).

Dengvaxia disaster

Dengvaxia is a failed dengue vaccine. Irrational design with no understanding of disease mechanism led to this fiasco (27).

Influenza shock syndrome

Influenza vaccine provides unreliable short term protection while increasing risk of influenza shock syndrome (28,29).

Conclusion

The solutions for GAVIDOTTIR diseases include immediately removing all non-target antigens from all vaccines using technologies such as affinity chromatography(30).

Given the enormous damage caused by vaccines, the need for every vaccine must be re-evaluated. Many iatrogenic diseases such as measles related encephalitis/SSPE, polio complications are preventable by avoiding intramuscular and subcutaneous injections. Vaccines must be redesigned to account for all of the above problems.

References

1. Shoenfeld Y, Agmon-Levin N. "ASIA" - autoimmune/inflammatory syndrome induced by adjuvants. *J Autoimmun.* England; 2011 Feb;36(1):4–8.
2. Vaccine Excipient & Media Summary [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2016 Jan 16]. Available from: <http://www.cdc.gov/vaccines/pubs/pinkbook/downloads/appendices/B/excipient-table-2.pdf>
3. Arumugham V, Trushin M V. Role of NMDA receptor autoimmunity induced by food protein containing vaccines, in the etiology of autism, type 1 diabetes, neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. *Int J Pharm Res.* 2019 Mar 1;11(1):428–37.
4. National Academies of Sciences and Medicine E. Finding a Path to Safety in Food Allergy: Assessment of the Global Burden, Causes, Prevention, Management, and Public Policy. Stallings VA, Oria MP, editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2017.
5. Arumugham V. Aeroallergen contamination of multi-dose and reconstituted vaccine vials cause the development of asthma, gastrointestinal diseases and proves vaccine makers and vaccine safety regulators are incompetent [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Jan 22]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2544037>
6. Arumugham V. Vaccination with bovine, chick, yeast antigens synthesizes cross-reactive antibodies targeting human acetylcholine receptor and MuSK protein to cause Myasthenia Gravis: Confirmed by natural experiment (VAERS data), bioinformatics, case reports, animal experiments and titer study [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Sep 16]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3421558>
7. Arumugham V. Evidence that Food Proteins in Vaccines Cause the Development of Food Allergies and Its Implications for Vaccine Policy. *J Dev Drugs.* OMICS International; 2015 Oct;04(04):1–3.
8. Arumugham V. Vaccines and the development of food allergies: the latest evidence [Internet]. *BMJ.* 2016. Available from: <https://www.bmj.com/content/355/bmj.i5225/rr-0>
9. Arumugham V. How to prevent or reduce risk of food allergies, autism, asthma and type 1 diabetes: From a parent who has been burned [Internet]. 2018. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2061370>
10. Arumugham V. Vaccines and Biologics injury table based on mechanistic evidence – Mar 2019 [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 May 16]. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/record/2582635/files/viittoc0302http.pdf?download=1>
11. Arumugham V, Trushin M V. Autism pathogenesis: Piecing it all together, from end to beginning *J Pharm Sci Res.* 2018;10(11):2787–9.
12. Arumugham V. Role of NMDA receptor autoimmunity induced by food protein containing vaccines, in the etiology of autism, type 1 diabetes, neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. 2018.

13. Arumugham V. Milk containing vaccines cause milk allergies, EoE, autism and type 1 diabetes [Internet]. The BMJ. 2018. Available from: <https://www.bmj.com/content/361/bmj.k2396/rr>
14. Arumugham V. Bioinformatics and epidemiological evidence link yeast protein containing HPV and Hepatitis B vaccines to numerous autoimmune disorders such as vitiligo, narcolepsy, hypothyroidism, systemic lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis [Internet]. 2018. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1435403>
15. Arumugham V. Atopic dermatitis caused by vaccine-induced allergy to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*? [Internet]. 2016. Available from: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/1034567>
16. Arumugham V, Trushin M V. Cancer immunology, bioinformatics and chemokine evidence link vaccines contaminated with animal proteins to autoimmune disease: a detailed look at Crohn's disease and Vitiligo. *J Pharm Sci Res.* 2018;10(8):2106.
17. Arumugham V. Bioinformatics analysis links type 1 diabetes to vaccines contaminated with animal proteins and autoreactive T cells express skin homing receptors consistent with injected vaccines as causal agent [Internet]. 2017. Available from: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/1034775>
18. Arumugham V. Correlation of type 1 diabetes trends in European countries to the number of bovine insulin and GAD65 contaminated chick embryo cell culture containing vaccines in the schedule, as predicted by the autoimmunity mechanism involving immunization with homolo [Internet]. 2018. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1870364>
19. Arumugham V. Vaccines cause autoimmune diseases: The latest evidence implicates influenza, tetanus, diphtheria, and pertussis (Tdap), human papilloma virus, pneumococcal, hepatitis A, hepatitis B, typhoid, yellow fever, and Japanese encephalitis vaccines in Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD) [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Jun 12]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3244630>
20. Arumugham V. Autoepitopes (22 of 27) in rheumatoid arthritis differ from vaccine antigens by a single amino acid residue, ideal for low affinity self reactive T cell mediated autoimmunity and aluminum adjuvant promotes citrullination of vaccine antigens thus the synthesis of ACPA [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Sep 10]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3382978>
21. Arumugham V. Role of animal, food, fungal protein containing vaccines, insulin injections and gastric acid inhibition therapy in the etiology of celiac disease [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 Aug 24]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3370427>
22. Rubin K, Glazer S. The potential role of subclinical *Bordetella Pertussis* colonization in the etiology of multiple sclerosis. *Immunobiology.* 2015 Dec 18;
23. Lee ST, Bracci P, Zhou M, Rice T, Wiencke J, Wensch M, et al. Interaction of allergy history and antibodies to specific varicella-zoster virus proteins on glioma risk. *Int J Cancer.* 2014;134(9):2199–210.
24. Goldman GS, King PG. Review of the United States universal varicella vaccination program: Herpes zoster incidence rates, cost-effectiveness, and vaccine efficacy based primarily on the Antelope Valley Varicella Active Surveillance Project data. *Vaccine.* 2013.
25. Vaccine Injury Table [Internet]. [cited 2019 Feb 2]. Available from: <https://www.hrsa.gov/sites/default/files/vaccinecompensation/vaccineinjurytable.pdf>

26. Allan S. Cunningham. Injections and acute flaccid myelitis: the dog that hasn't barked [Internet]. BMJ. 2018 [cited 2019 Oct 5]. p. k5246. Available from: <https://www.bmj.com/content/363/bmj.k5246/rr>
27. Arumugham V. Irrational dengue vaccine designs that ignore IgE and IgG4 mediated effects are destined to follow in Dengvaxia's disastrous direction? [Internet]. 2018. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1476291>
28. Arumugham V. Influenza vaccines and dengue-like disease [Internet]. The BMJ. 2018. Available from: <https://www.bmj.com/content/360/bmj.k1378/rr-15>
29. Arumugham V. Influenza and acellular pertussis vaccines not only fail to protect, they increase susceptibility and severity of disease upon infection – benefits are overrated and the risks are being ignored [Internet]. 2019. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2532166>
30. Zhao M, Vandersluis M, Stout J, Haputs U, Sanders M, Jacquemart R. Affinity chromatography for vaccines manufacturing: Finally ready for prime time? Vaccine. Netherlands; 2018 Apr;